

Synthesis, spectral and antibacterial studies on bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives with Schiff bases of benzil- α -monoxime

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Abstract : A series of complexes of the type $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Hf(L)}]$ (L = Schiff base ligand (LH₂), derived by condensing benzil- α -monoxime and aromatic and aliphatic diamines) has been prepared. Tentative structures of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (IR, electronic and ¹H NMR) data. Proton NMR spectra indicate that there is rapid rotation of the cyclopentadienyl ring around the metal-ring axis on the NMR time scale at 25 °C. Studies were conducted to assess the growth inhibiting potential of the complexes synthesized and the ligands against various bacterial strains.

Keywords : Hafnium, Schiff base, benzil- α -monoxime.

Recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis and characterization of transition metal complexes containing Schiff base as ligands¹. Transition metal complexes with Schiff bases containing nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms make significant contributions to biological systems². Our interest^{3,4} in the synthesis and characterization of organohafnium(IV) complexes has been extended to Schiff base ligands derived from benzil- α -monoxime.

Results and discussion

The condensation reactions of benzil- α -monoxime with aliphatic and aromatic diamines (ethylenediamine, *o*-phenylenediamine, *p*-phenylenediamine, 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine, 2,6-diaminopyridine or *p*-diaminobiphenyl) in 2 : 1 molar ratio, respectively, give rise to imine oxime ligands (1).

A systematic study of reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chloride with Schiff bases (1) (molar ratio 1 : 1) in anhydrous THF in the presence of triethylamine have been studied. The complexes of type $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Hf(L)}]$ are obtained according to the following reaction :

where LH₂ = BEAH₂, OBMPAH₂, BPAH₂, PBPAH₂, OBPAH₂ or BBPAH₂.

R = CH₂CH₂ (BEAH₂), C₆H₃(CH₃) (OBMPAH₂), C₅H₃N (BPAH₂), *p*-C₆H₄ (PBPAH₂), *o*-C₆H₄ (OBPAH₂), C₆H₄-C₆H₄ (BBPAH₂)

Physical properties and elemental analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1. The resulting complexes are coloured solids, soluble in tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide, nitrobenzene. The molar conductances of the complexes in dimethylformamide are in the range of 5–12 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, which are well below the range observed for univalent electrolytes in this solvent.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes show a broad band in at ca. 440 nm that can be assigned⁴ to a charge-

Table 1. Reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) with Schiff bases of benzil- α -monoxime

Reactants taken (molar ratio)	Solvent	Stirring time (h)	Product, Colour	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	Hf
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + BEAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	12	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BEA)] Brown	68	61.2 (61.5)	4.2 (4.4)	7.0 (7.2)	22.4 (22.8)
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + OBMPAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	16	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(OBMPA)] Brown	62	64.0 (64.1)	4.0 (4.3)	6.4 (6.6)	21.0 (21.2)
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + BPAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	14	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BPA)] Dark brown	65	62.0 (62.2)	3.9 (4.0)	8.3 (8.4)	21.4 (21.5)
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + PBPAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	20	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(PBPA)] Light brown	70	63.5 (63.7)	4.0 (4.1)	6.6 (6.8)	21.3 (21.5)
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + OBPAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	18	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(OBPA)] Dark brown	60	63.6 (63.7)	4.0 (4.1)	6.6 (6.8)	21.4 (21.5)
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl ₂ + BBPAH ₂ + Et ₃ N (1 : 1 : 2)	THF	15	[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BBPA)] Brown	64	66.1 (66.3)	4.1 (4.2)	6.0 (6.2)	19.6 (19.7)

BEAH₂ = 1,2-Bis(benzil- α -monoxime)ethyl azomethine, OBMPAH₂ = 1,2-bis(benzil- α -monoxime)-2-methyl phenyl azomethine, BPAH₂ = 2,6-bis(benzil- α -monoxime)pyridine azomethine, PBPAH₂ = 1,4-bis(benzil- α -monoxime)phenyl azomethine, OBPAH₂ = 1,2-bis(benzil- α -monoxime)phenyl azomethine, BBPAH₂ = 4,4'-bis(benzil- α -monoxime)biphenyl azomethine.

transfer, a result in accord with their $(n-1)d^0ns^0$ electronic configuration. The ligands show three absorption maxima at *ca.* 220, 270 and 520 nm which are assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions associated with imine and phenyl functions of the ligands. In their respective complexes, these bands shift slightly to higher frequencies.

Infrared spectra :

Cyclopentadienyl group vibrations : Absorption bands occurring at *ca.* 3000 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(\text{C-H})$, *ca.* 1430 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(\text{C-C})$ and *ca.* 1020 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(\text{C-H})$ in all the complexes are assigned to the cyclopentadienyl group and indicate that these groups are π -bonded to metal⁵.

Oxime group vibrations : The IR spectra of ligands exhibit broad, medium intensity band around 3200 cm⁻¹, which is assigned⁶ to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ of the oxime group. However, in complexes this band disappears indicating the formation of bond between metal and oxygen. This is also confirmed by the appearance of band at *ca.* 430–420 cm⁻¹ assignable⁷ to $\nu(\text{Hf-O})$. The medium intensity band around 1580–1570 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligands are assigned⁷ to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (oxime), which remains almost at the same position in the complexes, indicating the C=N groups are not involved in bond formation.

Azomethine group vibration : The infrared spectra of Schiff bases show band at *ca.* 1620–1610 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to $\nu(\text{C=N})$, formed by the combination of keto group of benzil- α -monoxime with amino group of diamines. In the complexes, this band also remains almost at the same position indicating non-coordination of

C=N group with metal. The ligand BPAH₂ and its corresponding hafnium(IV) complexes show weak bands at *ca.* 1550, 620 and 440 cm⁻¹ assignable to pyridine ring deformation bands.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and complexes have been recorded in deuterated dimethylsulphoxide. The line intensities were determined by planimetric integration. The complexes show signal at δ 6.60–6.80, which may be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl ring protons and indicate the rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis. A signal in all ligands at *ca.* δ 8.20–8.52 may be assigned to the proton of oxime group which disappears in their corresponding complexes indicating the displacement of hydrogen of oxime group. The multiplet at *ca.* 7.50–7.78 may be due to aromatic ring protons. The ligand BPAH₂ and its corresponding complex show multiplet at δ 8.10–8.25 due to pyridine ring. OBMPAH₂ and its corresponding complexes show signal at *ca.* δ 2.2 due to CH₃ group.

Antibacterial activity : The antibacterial activity was evaluated against Gram positive *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram negative *Escherichia coli* by the paper-disc plate method⁸. The results (Table 2) show that activity increases on chelation. The activity of the ligands is affected by the nature of substituents; this in relation to the lipophilicity of the ligands and their membrane permeability, a key factor in determining their entry inside the cell.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of Schiff base ligands and their corresponding bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
BEAH ₂	2	3
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BEA)]	8	5
OBPAH ₂	6	8
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(OBPA)]	8	10
PBPAH ₂	5	5
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(PBPA)]	8	8
OBMPAH ₂	12	10
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(OBMPA)]	16	16
BPAH ₂	12	12
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BPA)]	16	16
BBPAH ₂	6	4
[(η^5 -C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Hf(BBPA)]	9	7
Ampicillin	35	35

The results lead to the following conclusions :

(a) The complexes are slightly more toxic than the parent ligands.

(b) The complexes with ligands derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine (BPAH₂) and 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (OBMPAH₂) show best activity against both *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*. This indicates the presence of -CH₃ group or pyridine nucleus increases the activity.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out strictly under anhydrous conditions. THF was dried by heating under reflux over sodium wire. Et₃N was purified by published method⁹. Bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chloride was purchased from Aldrich. Elemental analysis and physical measurements were made as noted earlier⁴. The ligands were prepared as reported in the literature¹⁰.

Preparation of complexes : To a solution of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chloride (20 mmol) in

dry THF (*ca.* 40 cm³) was added the appropriate ligand (20 mmol). To the resulting clear solution, Et₃N (40 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for *ca.* 12–15 h at room temperature. Precipitated Et₃N.HCl was removed by filtration and the volume of the solution was reduced to *ca.* 20 cm³ under reduced pressure. Dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) (20 cm³) was then added. The coloured precipitate, thus obtained, was thoroughly washed with Et₂O and recrystallized from 1 : 1 THF : Et₂O.

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